

ON EIGEN-VALUES AND PARTICULAR SOLUTIONS OF A SECOND ORDER LINEAR INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL OPERATOR

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Abstract

In the present paper we study finding the eigen values λ_k satisfying the integro-differential equation (1) and boundary condition (2) and appropriate particular solutions $y_k(x, \lambda)$.

Keywords: integro-differential equation, eigenvalue, particular solution, orthonormal, boundary value problem, transcendental functions, parameter, continuous, integral, equation.

Introduction

In the paper we study finding the solution of the integro-differential $(i - d)$ equation

$$y''(x) + [\lambda p(x) - g(x)]y(x) = \lambda \int_a^b k(x, s)y'(s)ds \quad (1)$$

the particular solutions $y_k(x, \lambda)$ satisfying the boundary condition

$$\left. \begin{aligned} y'(a) &= \alpha_1 y(a) + \beta_1 y(b), \\ y'(b) &= \alpha_2 y(a) + \beta_2 y(b) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

and the eigen-values λ_k corresponding to this solution.

Assume that the functions $p(x)$ and $g(x)$ involved in integro-differential equation (1) are continuous functions on the segment $[a, b]$ and satisfying the condition

$$p(x) > 0, g(x) > 0 \text{ in this segment.}$$

The function $K(x, s) > 0$ itself and the partial derivative $\frac{\partial k(x, s)}{\partial s} > 0$ are continuous functions in the rectangle $[a \leq x, y \leq b]$.

In addition, assume that the conditions

$$\beta_2 < 0, \alpha_1 > 0, \alpha_2 + \beta_1 = 0 \quad (3)$$

involved in the boundary condition (2) are satisfied.

There arises a question: under which conditions does the problem (1),(2) have non-zero eigen-values.

If in integro-differential equation (1) we write $\lambda = \lambda_m$ and $y(x) = y_m(x)$, then

$$y_m''(x) + [\lambda_m p(x) - g(x)]y_m(x) = \lambda_m \int_a^b k[x, s]y_m'(s)ds.$$

Hence we obtain

$$y_m''(x) + [\lambda_m p(x) - g(x)]y_m(x) - \lambda_m [k(x, b)y_m(b) - k(x, a)y_m(a)] = \lambda_m \int_a^b \frac{\partial k(x, s)}{\partial s} y_m(s)ds. \quad (4)$$

Multiply the both hand sides of the equality (4) by $y_m(x)dx$ and integrate the obtained expression from a to b , then

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_a^b y_m''(x)y_m(x)dx + \int_a^b [\lambda_m p(x)y_m^2(x)dx - \\ & - \int_a^b g(x)y_m^2(x)dx - \lambda_m [y_m(b) \int_a^b k(x, b)y_m(x)dx - \\ & - y_m(a) \int_a^b k(x, a)y_m(x)dx = \lambda_m \left[\int_a^b \frac{\partial k(x, s)}{\partial s} y(s)ds \right] y_m(x)dx \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

At the same time, we obtain

$$\int_a^b y_m''(x)y_m(x)dx = y_m(b)y_m'(b) - y_m(a)y_m'(a) - \int_a^b [y_m'(x)]^2 dx \quad (6)$$

Taking into account the expression $\int_a^b y_m''(x)y_m(x)dx$ of the equality (6) in (5)

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_m \int_a^b p(x)y_m^2(x)dx &= \int_a^b g(x)y_m^2(x)dx + \int_a^b (y_m'(x))^2 dx - \\ &- [y_m(b)y_m'(b) - y_m(a)y_m'(a)] - \\ &- \lambda_m \int_a^b \left[k(x,b) - k(x,a) - \int_a^b \frac{\partial k(x,s)}{\partial s} y(s)ds \right] y_m(x)dx. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_m \left[\int_a^b p(x)y_m^2(x)dx + \int_a^b \left[k(x,b) - k(x,a) - \int_a^b \frac{\partial k(x,s)}{\partial s} y(s)ds \right] y_m(x)dx \right] = \\ = \int_a^b g(x)y_m^2(x)dx + \int_a^b (y_m')^2 dx [y_m(b)y_m'(b) - y_m(a)y_m'(a)] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

By the condition, since $p(x) > 0$, $g(x) > 0$, $k(x,s) > 0$, $\frac{\partial k(x,s)}{\partial s} > 0$ for $\forall m \in N$ for the eigen values λ_m to be non-zero, from the equality (7) the inequalities

$$y_m(b)y_m'(b) < y_m(a)y_m'(a) \quad (8)$$

and

$$k(x,b) - k(x,a) > \int_a^b \frac{\partial k(x,s)}{\partial s} y_m(s)ds \quad (9)$$

should be valid.

2. Orthogonality condition for the eigen-values of the integro-differential operator.

Assume that (1)-(2) is a boundary value problem.

There exist the eigen-values λ_m and λ_n ($\lambda_m \neq \lambda_n$) and corresponding particular solution $y_m(x), y_n(x)$.

Then we can write

$$y_m''(x) + [\lambda_m p(x) - g(x)]y_m(x) = \lambda_m \int_a^b k(x,s)y_m'(\xi)d\xi \quad (10)$$

and

$$y_n''(x) + [\lambda_n p(x) - g(x)]y_n(x) = \lambda_n \int_a^b k(x,s)y_n'(\xi)d\xi \quad (11)$$

From (10) and (11) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (\lambda_m - \lambda_n) \int_a^b p(x)y_m(x)y_n(x)dx &= [y_m(x)y_n'(x) - y_n(x)y_m'(x)]_a^b + \\ &+ (\lambda_m - \lambda_n) \int_a^b \int_a^b k(x,s)[y_m'(s)y_n(s) - y_n'(s)y_m(s)]dsdx. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Using the boundary condition (2), we simplify the right hand side of (12).%

$$\begin{aligned} & [y_m(x)y_n'(x) - y_n(x)y_m'(x)]_a^b + \\ & + (\lambda_m - \lambda_n) \int_a^b \int_a^b k(x,s)[y_m'(s)y_n(s) - y_n'(s)y_m(s)]dsdx = \\ & = y_m'(b)y_n(b) - y_n'(b)y_m(b) - y_m'(a)y_n(a) + y_n'(a)y_m(a) + \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + (\lambda_m - \lambda_n) \int_a^b \int_a^b k(x, s) [y'_m(s) y_n(s) - y'_n(s) y_m(s)] ds dx = \\
& = [\alpha_2 y_m(a) + \beta_2 y_m(b)] y_n(b) - [\alpha_2 y_n(a) + \beta_2 y_n(b)] y_m(b) - \\
& - [\alpha_1 y_m(a) + \beta_1 y_m(b)] y_n(a) + [\alpha_1 y_n(a) + \beta_1 y_n(b)] y_m(a) + \\
& + (\lambda_m - \lambda_n) \int_a^b \int_a^b k(x, s) [y'_m(s) y_n(x) - y'_n(s) y_m(x)] ds dx = \\
& = (\alpha_2 + \beta_1) (y_m(a) y_n(b) - y_m(b) y_n(a)) + \\
& + (\lambda_m - \lambda_n) \int_a^b \int_a^b k(x, s) [y'_m(s) y_n(x) - y'_n(s) y_m(x)] ds dx. \tag{13}
\end{aligned}$$

Taking into account (13) in (11),

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\lambda_m - \lambda_n) \left[\int_a^b p(x) y_m(x) y_n(x) dx - \int_a^b \int_a^b k(x, s) [y'_m(s) y_n(x) - y'_n(s) y_m(x)] ds dx \right] = \\
& = (\alpha_2 + \beta_1) (y_m(a) y_n(b) - y_m(b) y_n(a)). \tag{14}
\end{aligned}$$

From $\lambda_m \neq \lambda_n$ and the condition $\alpha_2 + \beta_1 = 0$ we obtain the orthogonality condition of the particular solution of the integro-differential operator

$$\left[\int_a^b p(x) y_m(x) y_n(x) dx - \int_a^b \int_a^b k(x, s) [y'_m(s) y_n(x) - y'_n(s) y_m(x)] ds dx \right] = 0.$$

3. Let the linearly independent solutions $y_1(x, \lambda), y_2(x, \lambda)$ of the integro-differential equation (1) satisfy the Cauchy initial condition

$$\left. \begin{aligned} y_1(a, \lambda) &= 1 & y'_1(a, \lambda) &= 0 \\ y_2(a, \lambda) &= 0 & y'_2(a, \lambda) &= 1 \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{15}$$

In this case, the general solution of the integro-differential equation (1) is in the following form

$$y(x) = c_1 y_1(x, \lambda) + c_2 y_2(x, \lambda) \tag{16}$$

Here we find the arbitrary constants C_1 and C_2 from the boundary conditions (2) and using the initial condition we (15):

$$\begin{aligned}
y'_1(b, \lambda) &= \alpha_2 + \beta_2 y_1(b, \lambda) \\
y'_2(b, \lambda) &= \beta_2 y_2(b, \lambda); \quad \beta_1 y_1(b, \lambda) + \alpha_1 = 0;
\end{aligned}$$

We obtain $\beta_2 y_2(b, \lambda) - 1 = 0$. Taking these into account in (16), for finding the constants C_1 and C_2

$$\left. \begin{aligned} c_1 [y'_1(b, \lambda) - \beta_2 y_1(b, \lambda) - \alpha_1] + c_2 [y'_2(b, \lambda) - \beta_2 y_2(b, \lambda)] &= 0 \\ c_1 [\alpha_2 y_1(b, \lambda) - \alpha_1] + c_2 [\alpha_2 y_2(b, \lambda) - 1] &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{17}$$

For the system of equations (17) to have non-zero solution for $c_1 \neq 0; c_2 \neq 0$

$$W(\lambda) = \begin{vmatrix} y'_1(b, \lambda) - \beta_2 y_1(b, \lambda) - \alpha_1 & y'_2(b, \lambda) - \beta_2 y_2(b, \lambda) \\ \alpha_2 y_1(b, \lambda) - \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 y_1(b, \lambda) - 1 \end{vmatrix} = 0. \tag{18}$$

From (18) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
W(\lambda) &= \alpha_2 [y_1(b, \lambda)y_2'(b, \lambda) - y_1'(b, \lambda)y_2(b, \lambda)] + \\
&+ y_1'(b, \lambda) - \beta_2 y_1(b, \lambda) - \alpha_1 - (\alpha_2^2 + \alpha_1 \beta_2)y_2(b, \lambda) + \\
&+ \alpha_1 y_2(b, \lambda) = (\alpha_2 - \alpha_1) + (\alpha_2^2 - \alpha_1 \beta_1)y_2(b, \lambda) + \\
&+ y_1'(b, \lambda) - \beta_2 y_2(b, \lambda) = 0 \\
W(\lambda) &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Since the function $W(\lambda)$ is a complex transcendental function at all the values of λ the parameter λ being the solution of the transcendental equation $W(\lambda) = 0$ is an eigen value of the boundary value problem (1),(2).

It should be noted that if $\lambda = \lambda_k$ is any solution of the characteristic equation (19), denoting arbitrary constant C_1 from the system of equations (17) by $C_1 = C_k$ from the system of equations (17)

$$c_2 = c_k \frac{\alpha_2 + \beta_2 y_1(b, \lambda_k) - y_1'(b, \lambda_k)}{y_2'(b, \lambda_k) - \beta_2 y_2(b, \lambda_k)}. \tag{20}$$

Taking this value of the constant C_2 in (16), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
y_k(x) &= c_k y_1(x, \lambda_k) + \\
&+ c_k \frac{\alpha_2 + \beta_2 y_1(b, \lambda_k) - y_1'(b, \lambda_k)}{y_2'(b, \lambda_k) - \beta_2 y_2(b, \lambda_k)} y_2(b, \lambda_k) = \\
&= c_k \frac{\begin{vmatrix} y_1(x, \lambda_k) & y_2(x, \lambda_k) \\ y_1'(b, \lambda_k) & y_2'(b, \lambda_k) \end{vmatrix} - \beta_2 \begin{vmatrix} y_1(x, \lambda_k) & y_2(x, \lambda_k) \\ y_1(b, \lambda_k) & y_2(b, \lambda_k) \end{vmatrix} + \alpha_2 y_2(x, \lambda_k)}{\begin{vmatrix} y_2'(b, \lambda_k) & \beta_2 \\ y_2(b, \lambda_k) & 1 \end{vmatrix}}
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

In (21) given the values $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, we obtain the particular solutions $y_k(x) (k = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$ corresponding to the eigen-values $\lambda_k (k = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$. These particular solutions satisfy the boundary value problem (1),(2). Note that the function $y_k(x)$ determined by the equality (21) for $x = a$ can not be equal to zero as an identify according to the initial condition (15).

Indeed, according to the condition (15), from (21) we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
y_k(x) &= \frac{\begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ y_1'(b, \lambda_k) & y_2'(b, \lambda_k) \end{vmatrix} - \beta_2 \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ y_2(b, \lambda_k) & y_2(b, \lambda_k) \end{vmatrix} + \alpha_2 \cdot 0}{y_2'(b, \lambda_k) - \beta_2 y_2(b, \lambda_k)} = \\
&= c_k \frac{y_2'(b, \lambda_k) - \beta_2 y_2(b, \lambda_k)}{y_2'(b, \lambda_k) - \beta_2 y_2(b, \lambda_k)} = c_k.
\end{aligned}$$

4. When the function $f(x)$ is continuous in the segment $[a, b]$, we look for the solution satisfying the integro-differential equation

$$y''(x) - [\lambda p(x) - g(x)]y(x) + \lambda \int_a^b k(x, s)y_m'(s)ds = f(x) \tag{22}$$

and the boundary condition

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_1(y) &= y'(a) - \alpha_1 y(a) - \beta_1 y(b) = 0 \\ u_2(y) &= y'(b) - \alpha_2 y(a) - \beta_2 y(b) = 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{23}$$

in the form of

$$z(x) = z_0(x) + \lambda z_1(x) + \lambda^2 z_2(x) + \dots + \lambda^k z_k(x) + \dots \quad (24)$$

given by the powers of the parameter λ .

Here $z_k(x)$ ($k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$) is the function of x . Taking into account the expression $z(x)$ from (24) in (22), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} & z_0''(x) + \lambda z_1''(x) + \lambda^2 z_2''(x) + \dots + \lambda^k z_{k_2}''(x) + \dots + \\ & + [\lambda p(x) - g(x)] [z_0(x) + \lambda z_1(x) + \lambda z_2^2(x) + \dots + \lambda^k z_k(x) + \dots + \\ & + \lambda \int_a^b k(x, s) [z_0'(s) + \lambda z_1'(s) + \lambda z_2'(s) + \dots + \lambda^k z_2'(s) + \dots] ds = f(x). \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Equating the same order coefficients of λ in (25) and taking into account (24) in (23), for finding $z_k(x)$, ($k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$) we obtain the following boundary value problem.

$$z_0''(x) - g(x)z_0(x) = f(x) \quad (26)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_1(z_0) &= 0 \\ u_2(z_0) &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (26')$$

$$z_1''(x) + p(x)z_0(x) - g(x)z_1(x) + \int_a^b k(x, s) z_1'(s) ds = 0 \quad (27)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_1(z_1) &= 0 \\ u_2(z_1) &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (27')$$

and for any k

$$z_k''(x) + p(x)z_{k-1}(x) - g(x)z_k(x) + \int_a^b k(x, s) z_{k-1}'(s) ds = 0 \quad (28)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_1(z_k) &= 0 \\ u_2(z_k) &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (28')$$

At first we look for the solution satisfying the equation (26). It is known that if $z_1(x)$ and $z_2(x)$ are linearly independent solutions of the equation $z_0''(x) - g(x)z(x) = 0$, then is a general solution of the homogeneous equation $z_0(x) = c_1 z_1(x) + c_2 z_2(x)$.

Then according to the constant variation method, the general solution of the equation (27) is

$$z_0(x) = c_1 z_1(x) + c_2 z_2(x) + r_0(x) \quad (29)$$

here we denote

$$z_0(x) = z_1(x) \int_a^b z_2(x) f(x) dx - z_2(x) \int_a^b z_1(x) f(x) dx$$

Replacing the function $f(x)$ in the equation (26) by the function $p(x)z_{k-1}(x) + \int_a^b k(x, s) z_{k-1}'(s)$ from the equation (28), the general solution of the integro-differential equation (28) is denoted by

$$z_k(x) = z_1(x) \left[\int_a^b p(x) z_{k-1}(x) z_2(x) dx + \int_a^b \int_a^b k(x, s) z_{k-1}'(s) z_2(x) dx ds \right] -$$

$$-z_2(x) \left[\int_a^b p(x) z_{k-1}(x) z_1(x) dx + \int_a^b \int_a^b k(x,s) z_{k-1}'(s) z_1(x) dx ds \right] \quad (30)$$

Let the constants $c_1, c_2; c_1^k, c_2^k$ involved in the inequality be satisfied by the boundary conditions (26') and (27').

Then

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_1(z_0) = u_1(c_1 z_1 + c_2 z_2 + r_0(x) = c_1 u_1(z_1) + c_2 u_1(z_2) + u_1(z_0) = 0 \\ u_2(z_0) = u_2(c_1 z_1 + c_2 z_2 + r_0(x) = c_1 u_2(z_1) + c_2 u_2(z_2) + u_2(z_0) = 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (31)$$

and

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_1(z_k) = u_1(c_1^k z_1 + c_2^k z_2 + r_k) = c_1^k u_1(z_1) + c_2^k u_1(z_2) + u_1(z_k) = 0 \\ u_2(z_k) = u_2(c_1^k z_1 + c_2^k z_2 + r_k) = c_1^k u_2(z_1) + c_2^k u_2(z_2) + u_2(z_k) = 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (32)$$

From the system of equations

$$c_1 = \frac{u_1(z_2)u_2(r_0) - u_2(r_2)u_1(r_0)}{u_1(z_1)u_2(r_2) - u_1(r_2)u_2(z_1)}, \quad (33)$$

$$c_2 = \frac{u_1(r_0)u_2(z_1) - u_1(z_1)u_2(r_0)}{u_1(z_1)u_2(r_2) - u_1(z_2)u_2(z_1)}, \quad (34)$$

Taking into account (33) and (34) in (29)

$$\begin{aligned} z_0(x) = \frac{u_1(z_2)u_2(r_0) - u_2(r_2)u_1(r_0)}{u_1(z_1)u_2(r_2) - u_1(r_2)u_2(z_1)} z_1(x) - \\ - \frac{u_1(z_1)u_2(r_2) - u_1(r_0)u_2(z_1)}{u_1(z_1)u_2(z_2) - u_2(z_2)u_1(z_1)} z_2(x) + r_0(x). \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Show that

$$W(u_1; u_2) = u_1(z_1)u_2(z_2) - u_1(z_2)u_2(z_1) \neq 0 \quad (36)$$

Using the initial condition (15) and boundary condition (24), from (36) we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} W = u_1(z_1)u_2(z_2) - u_1(z_2)u_2(z_1) = -[\alpha_1 + \beta_1 z_1(b)] [z_2'(b) - \beta_2 z_2(b)] - \\ - [z_2'(b) - \beta_2 z_2(b)] [1 - \beta_1 z_2(b)] = (1 + \alpha_1) [\beta_2 z_2(b) - z_2'(b)] \neq 0 \end{aligned}$$

In the same way, finding c_1^k and c_2^k from the system of equations (32), taking them into account in (30):

$$\begin{aligned} z_k(x) = \frac{u_1(z_2)u_2(r_k) - u_2(z_2)u_1(z_k)}{W(u_1, u_2)} z_1(x) - \\ - \frac{u_2(r_k)u_1(z_1) - u_1(z_k)u_1(z_1)}{W(u_1, u_2)} z_2(x) + r_k(x). \end{aligned}$$

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